

Institutional Foundations of Migration Process Regulation: A Case Study of Arab Countries in the Middle East

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Abstract: This article analyzes migration processes in the Middle East region, their causes and consequences, prospects for developing cooperation between the countries of the region, and the role of international and regional organizations in this regard. The article highlights the obstacles to addressing the growing migration problem and offers suggestions on how to address them. In addition, the specificity of the approaches to migration, the similarities, and differences in the research conducted by scientists are covered in detail. The complexities of the migration process, the diversity of factors that lead to migration, and other important issues are also described. It is well known that the problem of migration is global in nature and many people are leaving their homes and families in search of a better life and income. However, in addition to the obvious economic benefits, migration also has other serious consequences. Serious problems that are likely to occur through this article have also been predicted, all proven by facts. In turn, the relevance of the approaches put forward in the article is also interpreted in terms of the functions they have been assigned based on the current state of the migration process.

Keywords: migration; security; economic migration; energy factor; demographic dynamics; humanitarian crisis; economic sectors; climate migration; natural factors; transnational characteristics; international and regional organizations; immigration; emigration; re-emigration; repatriation; refugee; asylum; the region; smuggling; border; demography; IOM

Introduction

It is known that the Global Agreement “On Safe, Orderly and Legal Migration” [1], adopted by the UN in 2018, is one of the important global documents related to the protection of labor migrants. According to it, the member states are obliged to implement the migration goals in accordance with the interests of the parties.

In 2015, the UN set the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030 to achieve health, gender equality, and safe, orderly and legal migration, in short, by protecting the rights of international migrants [2].

Migration as a complex phenomenon of social and political life requires the constant attention of both the state and professionals. The attention of experts is very important for the competent state authorities to develop competent recommendations on the regulation of migration flows and the adaptation of migrants to the new conditions for them. Migration varies because of the factors, scale, and nature that cause it. There are many proposed typologies and classifications of migration in the modern scientific literature, and the analysis of the phenomenon of migration as a subject of interdisciplinary research is more important from the point of view of different scientific approaches. After all, the process of migration is inextricably linked with the ethnic, economic, geographical, demographic, political moments of state life and its historical

development. Consequently, migration is a very broad concept, the object of study of a number of disciplines - economics, geography, history, sociology, political science, etc., which has a clear interdisciplinary character.

Institutional basis of regulating migration processes

Today, international non-governmental organizations, whose main activity is to help migrants and refugees, are facing a series of difficulties, and the process of helping migrants is becoming more and more complicated. The current situation not only limits the ability to provide services to immigrants, but also causes additional responsibilities to be imposed on state structures and the budget. As a result, negative attitudes towards the problem of migration, especially refugees, are growing among states and local populations.

The current situation based on xenophobic mood, in addition to limiting the ability to fully understand the urgency of the migration problem, is causing a decrease in the effectiveness of the migration policy, which allows for the development of mechanisms for combating many socio-economic and demographic problems.

Issues such as poverty and social inequality, fertility and disease, crime and human rights violations, discrimination and corruption do not constitute a complete set of social problems observed in receiving and sending countries in connection with migration flows.

In protecting the rights and interests of migrant workers by receiving countries, ratify the ILO Convention "On the Protection of the Rights of Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families", implement the global agreement "On Safe, Orderly and Legal Migration" and achieving the UN's sustainable development goals is required.

Analyzing the policy of the Middle East Arab countries to solve the migration problem, we can see that it has a bilateral and multilateral format.

The Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf. GCC is an example of a multidisciplinary format for regulating the migration policy of the Arab states of the Middle East. Accordingly, this association, which unites the rich Arab countries that receive the majority of migration flows in the region, aims to solve the existing problem together with the interested parties.

It is known that labor migration is multifaceted and important for the economic development of the GCC member states (Saudi Arabia, UAE, Qatar, Oman, Bahrain and Kuwait). At the same time, taking into account the individual development characteristics of each country, existing problems, and the development trends and prospects of the region, it is considered urgent to further reform the labor market.

In recent decades, the GCC has been acting as a special weighted council uniting member states. The late king of KSA, Fahd Ibn Abdulaziz, commented on the GCC and said, "This Council, becoming a model of integrated cooperation, should strengthen relations between Arab League member states and act as a shield in the fight against external threats"[3]. Today, the main direction of the cooperation of the Arab monarchies within the framework of the GCC is aimed at strengthening the defense capabilities of the member states, forming a common defense infrastructure, and ensuring regional security by conducting a unified foreign policy on a global scale. In 1994, within the framework of the GCC summit, for the first time, the member states officially developed a unified approach to "interpreting the true values and principles of Islam, based on the rejection of all forms of violence and the promotion of tolerance", which confirms our above opinion. [4].

In the 20th century, all the monarchies of the Arabian Peninsula achieved unprecedentedly high growth rates in terms of national income and living standards. This was achieved through a single industry, namely the production and export of hydrocarbons, and in this way they continued to join the ranks of developing countries. After the development of oil fields in these countries, foreign workers and experts began to be intensively attracted to the national economy.

As a result, the number of migration flows to the region increased between 1970-2000, that is, when the price of energy resources in the world market had a high index. However, this process caused not only positive but also negative consequences for the countries of the region. The conducted analyzes show that the current situation in the GCC member states has become increasingly negative in recent years. This, in turn, creates the need to reform national labor markets.

It should be noted that the member states of the GCC are not the only recipient countries in the world, but it is impossible not to recognize that these countries have formed a unique system of attracting labor resources. Today, the total number of labor migrants in the member states of the GCC, together with their family members, is more than 28 million people. This is about half of the population of member states of this association. At the same time, the percentage of immigrants varies significantly from country to country. Thus, in the UAE and Qatar, this indicator has reached the highest international level, which is 90%. However, it is noteworthy that labor migrants in all countries of the region have a significant impact on economic development and GDP. In some countries, 99 percent of the private sector workforce is made up of immigrants. The local population hardly participates in the economic life of the state. They work as employees or officials of administrative management bodies. The current factor caused an artificial increase in the number of jobs in state structures, and a further increase in the demand of foreign professionals from business circles. In fact, foreign experts also participate in the activities of important state bodies. For example, in recent decades, the service of Egyptian officers has been widely used in order to further improve the system of national intelligence services of the UAE. At the moment, it is impossible to achieve high goals related to the development of the state without attracting foreign experts to industries, infrastructure development, and services. At the same time, this process is a threat to the national security of all countries that are members of the GCC.

The existence of the opportunity to earn income from the export of energy resources, which are the national wealth of the states, that is, regardless of labor productivity, and to satisfy the shortage in the labor market at the expense of foreign labor and specialists, caused a decrease in the enthusiasm for hard work among the local population. As a result, among the citizens of the Arab monarchies, a feeling of not being so satisfied with working in the existing professions was formed. Based on the above, the current situation related to the alienation of the local population in the labor market can be assessed as a national tragedy. This, in turn, created the need to conduct personnel training policy among the population and educate young people in the spirit of national values.

It is known that in some countries of the European Union, due to the characteristics of the demographic growth rate, there is a shortage of the working-age population. However, the opposite can be seen in the case of countries such as Qatar and the UAE. After all, the GCC member states have high rates of demographic growth, and there is a tendency to increase the active population of people capable of working. However, it is increasingly impossible to use them as a labor resource in the real sector of the economy. All this has caused the unemployment rate to increase in the GCC member states in recent years. At the same time, in countries such as Saudi Arabia, Oman, Bahrain and Kuwait, there is a feeling of dissatisfaction among citizens related to the lack of jobs. This was followed by anti-government protests in the 2010s. In addition to the above, relations between the local population and immigrants are increasingly strained due to the rise of nationalism, accusations of labor market appropriation against migrants, an unfair competitive environment, the rise of crime involving immigrants, and the formation of a critical attitude towards migration policies. In the UAE and Qatar, despite the increase in the number of unemployed, there were no mass riots due to the high income of the population. However, it is natural that the current situation will affect the economic development and political stability of the country in the future.

Another important feature observed in relation to the migration situation in the countries of the Middle East region is related to the status of foreign workers and professionals. Unlike the

European Union countries, where there is equal rights and citizenship with local citizens, the situation in the Arab monarchies is significantly different. For example, citizenship of the GCC member states is granted to foreigners only as an exception, based on the decision of the top political leadership. As an exception in this regard, we can cite as an example the policy pursued in Bahrain in the last few years. It is known that in recent years Bahrain has been applying the practice of granting citizenship to more than 100,000 residents of other Arab countries. However, this situation is one of the temporary measures for certain political reasons. For this reason, English-language sources often use the term “expats”[5] instead of “migrants” when referring to foreign workers in GCC member states. After all, this term refers to visitors on a temporary basis.

In recent years, problems related to the use of slave labor, human rights violations and exploitation of migrant workers in many Arab monarchies remain one of the painful aspects of the migration policy in the Middle East region. Although it is natural for all the recipient countries to observe such problems, the current situation in the member states of the GCC is being seriously criticized by human rights organizations. In the countries of the Arabian Peninsula, the reform of the system of protection of the rights of labor migrants was also caused by the critical views of external forces. After all, caring for visiting migrants in the European Union is an important and integral part of migration policy. In the countries of the Arabian Peninsula, in recent years, attempts to regulate the migration situation and improve working conditions have been made, mainly through the adoption of legislation and the establishment of regulatory bodies. However, the situation in these countries is still not satisfactory.

In addition, the member states of the GCC did not join the 1951 UN Convention on the Status of Refugees. Today, the policy of the Gulf states to stabilize the migration situation in the Middle East region is primarily aimed at providing humanitarian assistance to internally displaced persons and refugees, and does not envisage receiving migrants on their territory. Thus, despite the critical views of the Western countries, the UN and a number of international organizations involved in the protection of human rights, the monarchies of the Arabian Peninsula did not express their desire to settle the citizens of Yemen and Syria in their territories not only as refugees, but also as labor migrants. It is noteworthy that citizens of Arab countries with a common language and culture are not a priority among foreign nationals seeking to enter the Arab countries of the Persian Gulf. This can be attributed to the host country leaders’ sense of danger from attempts to derail the domestic political situation by using the Arab diasporas. A change in the current trend is also likely in the near future.

GCC member states are an important source of income for donor countries. After all, migrant workers send a large part of their income to their homeland. In this case, the outflow volume of money mass that does not return to the economy is very high, and the figures given as of 2017 confirm our above opinion: 6.6% of GDP in Bahrain, 8.8% of GDP in Kuwait, 11.7% of GDP in Oman, 5.6% of GDP in Qatar , 4.7 percent of GDP in Saudi Arabia, 4.6 percent of GDP in the UAE. When comparing this indicator with other countries, it can be understood how high it is. In particular, in European countries such as France and Germany, which receive large numbers of immigrants, this indicator does not exceed 1 percent of GDP. The current situation is characterized not only by the high share of foreigners in the GCC member states, but also by the specific features of the migration policy. It is known that many immigrants do not have the opportunity to live together with their family members, and their rights in many areas are limited. Unlike immigrants in the European Union, they do not have the opportunity to buy real estate or engage in entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, it is difficult for them to integrate into society. The limited status of labor migrants, on the one hand, reduces their need for social protection, and on the other hand, allows them to take a large amount of their income out of the state. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the stability of the national currency of the receiving countries (especially taking into account the conversion of remittances into other currencies) and complicates their monetary policy. After all, recently, cases of using gray money transfer schemes, including the “Hawala” [6] system, in order to avoid mandatory payments have

become widespread. In this case, money, material assets in the form of gold and precious stones are transferred from one country to another without attaching financial documents. This has a serious impact on the state economy.

Today, a number of measures being taken in the GCC member states indicate that the government members are fully aware of its negative consequences. This can be seen in the example of public policies related to the strengthening of control over money transfers, the promotion of initiatives to increase the rights of workers, the simplification of the process of moving family members, the employer's focus on the issue of social protection of employees, and the formation of ownership rights to real estate. Most of the countries that ensure their economic stability at the expense of remittances sent from wealthy countries of the Middle East region. India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Egypt, and Sri Lanka are among the countries that benefit most from remittances from their expatriates today. It is also possible to include countries such as Morocco, Tunisia, Lebanon, Jordan, Nepal and Afghanistan, which are interested to a certain extent. Meanwhile, remittances to donor countries continue to move steadily. The preservation of the current situation depends primarily on the economic situation in the GCC member states, which is primarily determined by the price of oil on the world market. It should be noted that the unstable political situation observed in some countries of the region in recent years (for example, the political coups in Egypt in 2011-2013), as well as the migration policy of these countries did not significantly affect this process.

Above, we talked about the slow labor market regulation in the rich countries of the Middle East in recent decades. It is known that until the 1990s, no statistics were kept about the state units consisting of foreigners. In the late 1980s, Oman was one of the first to initiate reforms aimed at regulating the labor market. In the following years, other countries of the region, following his example, began to struggle with the implementation of a number of effective measures.

In recent years, the governments of all the member states of the GCC have been conducting a more active policy, taking into account the urgency of the problem of eliminating dependence on labor migrants and the need to regulate the labor market. Reforming the labor market, especially ensuring the participation of the local population in this regard, is one of the priorities of the economic policy of every state. In Qatar, which is one of the world's leading countries in terms of per capita income, has an important place "Qatarization". On the basis of this program, it is confirmed that the main attention should be focused on the issues of national personnel training policy and employment promotion in the activities of state agencies and large companies.

Among the measures that are widespread in the member states of the GCC, special attention is paid to the promotion of employment of the local population by introducing mandatory quotas, payment and benefits system, investing in education reform, improving the qualifications of national personnel, and regulating the state wage system. Compulsory payments are similar to tax revenues in terms of their status, but their size is not determined in relation to value added tax. In this case, the goal of the government representatives is to put pressure on the business by increasing the volume of mandatory payments, thereby ensuring the employment of local specialists and achieving an increase in budget revenues. Therefore, in recent years, there have been frequent cases of protests in countries such as Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, and Oman that the labor relations policies of the governing bodies have hindered business activities.

At the same time, efforts and influence measures aimed at stabilizing the migration situation are carried out depending on the specific characteristics of this or that country. For example, the rate of demographic growth in Qatar or the UAE has made it possible to implement many changes aimed at regulating the labor market. In Saudi Arabia and Oman, 10% of the demand for local labor can be met by migrant workers.

However, as a result of the existing reforms, not all countries of the region have achieved the same effect. This can be seen in the case of the state of Oman, where the policy of "Omanization" has been carried out for nearly 30 years. After all, the results put forward by the representatives of the government were not achieved. We can see this in the increasing

dependence on migrant workers and the increase in the unemployment rate among the local population. Attempts to regulate the labor market through the policy of nationalization in many other countries that are members of the GCC have not yielded significant results.

All this is characterized by the absence of real economic incentives. For example, in 2000-2010, due to the migration situation among the population, the sharp increase in the mood of protest and the serious nature of the problem related to its solution caused the serious concern of the Western European countries. In order to find a solution to this problem, the methods of active involvement of political forces are widely used. Nevertheless, despite the magnitude of the problems that have arisen in connection with the migration situation, there has been no downward trend in the flow of migrants in recent years. Despite the strengthening of control over the compliance of migrants with the requirements of the migration legislation and the use of measures to combat illegal migration by the law-enforcement bodies of these countries, the expected result was not achieved in this regard. On the contrary, the number of immigrants visiting these countries continued to grow. This is determined by the demand for cheap labor force in the form of labor migrants at the state level, the formation of a mood of protest against them, and the fact that it takes priority over the application of administrative measures in this regard. For example, by reforming the labor market in Eastern European countries in accordance with the mood of the citizens, it is impossible to abandon the immigrants from the Middle East and North African countries, who are beneficial for the economic development of the country. Therefore, it can be assumed that in the near future it will be impossible to achieve a certain result in terms of reforming the migration policy of European countries.

The current trend can also be observed in the case of the countries of the Arabian Peninsula. Unlike European countries, the demographic situation in these countries does not have a significant impact on migration processes, but high labor efficiency, cheap and skilled labor force plays an important role in the economic development of these countries. Therefore, attempts by the states to regulate this process do not allow to change the existing trends. There is no doubt that the current situation will become more serious in the future, but effective measures against it have not been developed so far. The fact that the migration policy of the member states of the GCC remains unique and the global experience of finding a solution to it is not fully formed is causing the current situation to become more serious.

Accordingly, we can conclude that in the near future there will be a significant demand for labor migrants in the countries of the GCC and they will continue to maintain their position as a source of employment and remittances. Although the expansion of state participation in the regulation of the labor market has been achieved, it is difficult to talk about the effectiveness of the activity in this regard.

Arab League. Speaking about the Arab League, it is worth mentioning a special aspect of this organization. Based on the content of the agreement signed in 1945, the goal of Arab League's activity is to "strengthen cooperation between the member states of the organization and for this purpose develop a unified political direction between the states and protect the independence and sovereignty of these parties within the interests of the Arab states and issues related to them". The scope of cooperation included not only political, but also economic, financial, communication, cultural, medical and social cooperation relations, as well as determining citizenship, issuing passports and visas, and extradition of criminals.

The unique aspect of this organization's activity is determined by the fact that, in addition to 18 Arabic-speaking countries and the Palestinian Authority, it was able to unite Muslim countries (Djibouti, Somalia and the Comoros Islands) located in East Africa (the population of which is not purely Arab). In a word, the organization is able to unite the richest countries of the region (Qatar, UAE, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Bahrain) and the poorest countries (Somalia, Comoros Islands, Mauritania, Yemen, Sudan, Djibouti), the Middle East and Africa. serves as an important connecting bridge between countries [7]. Harmonization of migration policies of the organization and its member states is of great importance in the regulation of the migration

processes studied within the framework of the research work. Accordingly, we will focus on the features of the policy of Arab League member states in this regard.

The League of Arab States hosted the fifth global meeting of the Arab regional consultation process on migration, which was established in 2014 and started in 2015. This meeting is an important regional consultation process on migration issues in recent years. Such activities organized by ADL are primarily aimed at maximally using migration processes as a positive factor, developing a comprehensive and integrated strategy of Arab countries, organizing regional and international negotiations on migration issues with the participation of interested parties and thus aims to strengthen the approaches of the countries in this regard, as well as to open new pages of cooperation between sending, receiving and transit countries. ADL's initiatives to regulate migration processes promoted in harmony with the goals of SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) are also reflected in its policy documents. In addition, in the framework of the regional consultation process with the participation of the Arab countries, in order to implement the goals of the SDG, it is planned to establish a mutual exchange of information and experience regarding the activities of the countries related to the migration policy, and to obtain practical results regarding the regulation of this process.

In order to improve the efficiency of regulation of migration processes within the framework of the League of Arab States activities, it is planned to coordinate national and international initiatives in the following ways: mutual analysis and synthesis of views and information at the national level and their use as a primary source in global processes; application of global goals to the national strategy of Arab countries, existing norms and standards; mobilizing member states of the organization in the process of cooperation aimed at regulating migration processes is one of them.

The tradition of receiving reports on the implementation of SDG goals related to migration is on the agenda of the organization's regularly organized annual meetings. In addition, technical assistance will be provided by the Economic and Social Commission of the United Nations and the International Organization for Migration in the implementation of the migration-related goals of the regional consultation process with the participation of the Arab countries.

In general, the following can be included among the main problems associated with migration processes in the Middle Eastern countries today: displacements and forced migration due to armed conflicts, extremist movements, increased poverty, food insecurity and climate change; illegal migration and mixed migration flows; such as human trafficking and migrant smuggling. At this point, it should be noted that there are the following issues that are being resolved in order to regulate these processes and find solutions to problems: lack of a unified definition of the term "international migrant"; that the process of determining the extent of international migration and collecting reliable data on it has not reached its perfection; including lack of transparency in data exchange.

To eliminate the above-mentioned shortcomings, to improve the development of research and analytical materials, to provide technical assistance to member states in the field of population census, data collection and preparation of analytical materials, to increase their potential in this regard, also, it is desirable to increase the activity of regional consultation processes on the implementation of the migration goals of the BRM for 2030 and to increase the effectiveness of the development of programs and the use of statistical data at the national level in order to support refugees and internally displaced persons [8].

Organisation of Islamic Cooperation. The OIC is one of the influential international intergovernmental organizations with a wide range of influence, which successfully promotes promising initiatives of international and interregional importance in the Islamic world. OIC actively participates in the development of cooperation between member states in the political, trade-economic, transport-communication and cultural-humanitarian spheres. Currently, the number of OIC member states has reached 57, and it has been able to unite about 1.5 billion people. It should be noted here that the Republic of Uzbekistan has been a full member of this

organization since October 2, 1996. The goal of the OIC activities is to establish cooperation between the member states in solving problems related to the development of Islamic civilization and current problems of international importance. The problem of migration is also one of the important issues on the organization's agenda. In recent years, many efforts have been made by IHT to solve this problem. As one of the important measures taken to solve the migration problem, we can mention the 8th session of the OIC Statistical Commission, which was held in Ankara, Turkey, on October 23-25, 2019. Representatives of OIC member states, as well as the Islamic Development Bank Group, the UN Department of Statistics, the UN Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia, the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the International Labor Organization took part in this event. Issues such as increasing the efficiency of using electronic data collection technologies in population registration, activating agricultural registration and developing national statistical systems related to international labor migration were put on the agenda of the meeting. According to the results of the session, the new strategic approaches of the Statistical Commission of the OIC for 2030 were discussed, and an agreement was reached on the development of indicators on international labor migration, the use of cartographic and satellite data, scanning, the establishment of cooperation and the exchange of experience [9].

The Pan-Arab Free Trade Area (PAFTA). In 1981, an agreement (Agreement to Facilitate and Develop InterArab Trade) on establishment and development of inter-Arab trade was concluded between ADL member states in order to form and liberalize a free trade area in the region. After that, in February 1997, the Socio-Economic Council of ADL adopted a declaration on the establishment of the Pan-Arab Free Trade Agreement (PAFTA), which unites 18 Arab countries. In some sources, it is also referred to as the Greater Arab Free Trade Area (GAFTA). Currently, Bahrain, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Yemen, Qatar, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, UAE, Palestinian Authority, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Sudan and Tunisia are members of the organization. Russian economist I.M. Batyrshin according to, the need to create a free trade area is characterized by the incomplete formation of cooperation in the political and economic spheres between the countries of the Persian Gulf. [10].

The United Nations Economic and Social Commission for West Asia (ESCWA). In accordance with the resolution of the UN Economic and Social Council, on August 9, 1973, the UN Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (آسيا لغربي والاجتماعية الاقتصادية اللجنة) was established, which included Bahrain, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Yemen, Qatar, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Covering Arab countries such as Morocco, Oman, UAE, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Sudan and Tunisia. The purpose of the organization's activities is to support the all-round economic and social development of the countries of the region, to strengthen their economic relations with each other and with other countries of the world, to study the situation related to economic problems in the region, in particular, labor migration, and to collect, evaluate and distribute statistical data in this regard.

The Organization of the Arab Oil Exporting Countries (in Arabic المصدرة العربية الدول منظمة , in English OAPEC) with the participation of countries such as Algeria, Bahrain, Egypt, Iraq, Qatar, Kuwait, Libya, UAE, Saudi Arabia, Syria and Tunisia in the regulation of migration processes in the Middle East region established cooperation relations within the framework of OAPEC. In addition, by 1994, six out of nineteen Arab countries were members of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), and as of 2017, 12 Arab countries were members of the World Trade Organization [11].

The head of the World Bank, Jim Yong Kim, said that the process of regional integration in the Middle East is going on in a complicated way. In his opinion, the process of integration in Europe had a significant impact on the development of countries, reduced poverty and inequality, and made it possible to expand trade relations. At this point, it was also emphasized that the instability and uncertainties in the world economy have a high impact on developing countries [12]. Accordingly, it is possible to achieve positive changes in this regard by

restructuring the mechanisms of the national economy of the Middle Eastern countries, diversifying and developing the bilateral relations of the Arab East.

According to the data provided by the IMF in 2021, it will be known that the unemployment rate in countries such as Bahrain and Saudi Arabia is much higher than before the pandemic. It is natural that it will take a long time to reduce the level of unemployment caused by the drastic reduction of jobs observed in the context of the pandemic. The situation that arose during the pandemic had a negative impact on certain segments of the population. Most of them are low-skilled workers, young people and migrant workers.

According to data, the unemployment rate among women and youth in 2020 was 6-10 percent. In this, not only the public sector, but also the increase in the level of unemployment in the private sector was observed[13].

The above-mentioned unemployment and social inequality situation is causing instability in the Middle East region. Although the mood of discontent among the population is not high compared to 2019, a relative increase was observed in 2021. However, the current protests are at risk of further escalation amid the spread of new diseases among the population, rising unemployment, food shortages and price hikes. All of this is creating the basis for the escalation of political instability in countries such as Iraq, Yemen, Libya, Lebanon and Tunisia. Political and social instability has led to large-scale refugee flows and, in turn, discontent in other countries. In 2020-2021, the total number of people who reached the pitiful level of poverty is 7 million. established a person[14].

It is known that in the context of the pandemic, immigrants are among the strata that have experienced a relatively difficult situation. At the international level, in the GCC member states, where immigrants have an advantage over the local population, the sharp increase in the unemployment rate has had a dramatic impact on the lifestyle of immigrants and the volume of remittances.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the cooperation of the Arab countries in the regulation of the migration problem in the Middle East is established on the basis of bilateral and multilateral formats. This can be seen in the example of the cooperation of the states within the framework of associations such as the Cooperation Council of the Arab States of the Persian Gulf, the League of Arab States, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Arab Free Trade Area, the UN Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia, and the Organization of Arab Oil Exporting States. According to the analysis, the total number of labor migrants in the member states of GCC is more than 28 million people. This is about half of the population of member states of this association. At the same time, the percentage of immigrants varies significantly from country to country. For example, in the UAE and Qatar, this indicator has reached the highest international level and is 90 percent.

The existence of the opportunity to earn income from the export of energy resources and to satisfy the shortage in the labor market at the expense of foreign labor and specialists, the decrease in the passion for hard work among the local population, and the alienation in the labor market can be assessed as a national tragedy. This, in turn, created the need to conduct personnel training policy among the population and educate young people in the spirit of national values. In addition, the member states of FKADHK are an important source of income for donor countries. After all, migrant workers send a large part of their income to their homeland. In this case, the outflow of the money mass that does not return to the economy is very high, and it is 4-12 percent of the GDP of the countries of the region. Compared to European countries, especially France and Germany, it does not exceed 1 percent of GDP.

In recent years, the relationship between the local population and immigrants has become increasingly strained due to the rise of nationalism, accusations of labor market appropriation against migrants, an unfair competitive environment, the rise of crime involving immigrants, and

the formation of a critical attitude towards migration policies. In the countries of the Arabian Peninsula, in recent years, attempts to regulate the migration situation and improve working conditions have been made, mainly through the adoption of legislation and the establishment of regulatory bodies. However, the situation in these countries is still not satisfactory.

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